

INFLUENCE OF RESIN ON INTRAPLY SHEAR BEHAVIOR IN PREPREG FABRIC FORMABILITY

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ABSTRACT

Formability of fabric-reinforced thermoset prepregs has been studied through investigation of intraply shear behavior for the manufacture of automotive structural composites. Two dry carbon fabric architectures, woven and NCF, together with their corresponding epoxy-based thermoset prepregs have been studied. Intraply shear behavior is characterized using bias extension (BE) and picture frame (PF) tests using a range of processing conditions of temperature and strain rate. The prepreg fabrics have been characterized similar to the prepregs to understand the influence of semi-cured resin on prepreg fabric formability. The shear deformation behavior of prepregs is found to be mainly driven by their fabric architectures yet significantly influenced in magnitude by resin. The results show the significance of the choice of process parameters on the prepreg shear deformation behavior. It is demonstrated that preheating the prepreg to temperatures considerably lower than required to initiate cure can make the shear formability of prepregs equivalent to the constituent (dry) reinforcement fabric.

1 INTRODUCTION

Historically, composite manufacturing has been facing challenges in achieving higher production rates, reduction of cycle times, consistent part quality etc. In this context, the automotive sector is exploiting automation in composite forming stages together with the development of snap-cure thermoset prepregs [1-3].

The formability of biaxial fiber-reinforced materials is supported by their ability to undergo large intraply shear deformation. Intraply shear behavior of woven fabrics has been studied extensively which has resulted in a large amount of useful data, including some benchmark studies and comprehensive reviews, for the research community [4-6]. On the other hand, woven prepregs having complex rheological behavior are not properly studied. Similarly, NCF (non-crimp fabric) reinforced materials are also very popular, yet their intraply shear behavior is not as widely studied as that of woven materials; and even less so for NCF reinforced prepregs.

The shear behaviour of biaxial structural fabrics is characterised from the in-plane shear tests of picture frame (PF) and bias extension (BE) tests [7-10]. The PF test induces uniform shearing of the test-specimen owing to its kinematic construction and makes the post-test analysis relatively simplified. However, it is extremely sensitive to specimen misalignment issues [8, 9]. The BE test, on the other hand, is somewhat insensitive to specimen misalignment but creates non-homogenous deformation across the test specimen making it more difficult to interpret results. The BE test has also been described to induce intraply slip in the case of dry fabrics as they reach relatively high shear angles [9, 10]. Being uncontrolled, unquantified and problematic to simulate, such intraply slip limits the exploration towards maximum shear angle as well as the shear behaviour when using the BE test.

This present work offers a comparison study between the intraply shear behavior of selected thermoset prepregs and their constituent dry reinforcement fabrics. This is performed in an attempt to isolate the influence of the prepregging resin on the overall in-plane shear deformation behavior of a prepreg across a range of shear rates and temperatures that are industrial-process relevant.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 MATERIALS AND TEST CONDITIONS

The two materials used here are epoxy-based thermoset preregs: a woven prepreg and an NCF prepreg. The woven prepreg consists of a twill weave fabric with an areal weight of 240 gsm. The NCF prepreg has a pillar-stitched reinforcement with an areal weight of 400 gsm. The woven prepreg has epoxy-based Resin#1 as a matrix material whereas the NCF prepreg contains epoxy-based Resin#2. Figure 1 shows a comparison of the viscosities of two resins as a function of temperature. It is to be noted that the prepreg with Resin#2 is developed specifically for high rate manufacture of components using compression moulding (press curing) processes. Typically, the two preregs can be used to manufacture components with a total cycle time of 3-5 minutes depending upon the cure temperature selected. The normal cure temperatures are between 130 °C – 150 °C.

Figure 1. The temperature-dependent viscosity curves for two types of epoxy-based resins used in the selected prepreg materials.

The test conditions used for both PF and BE methods using a range of temperature and shear rates are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Experimental tests and characterization parameters for the selected materials

Material	Test	Temperature (°C)	Stretch rate (mm/s)	Notes
Woven	BE	21, 40, 60, 80	1	Prepreg and fabric
	PF	21, 40, 60, 80	1	Prepreg only
NCF	BE	21, 40, 60	0.5, 1, 2	Prepreg and fabric
	PF	21, 40	0.5, 1, 2	Prepreg only

It should be noted that the dry fabrics of the corresponding preregs are also investigated similar to the preregs in the case of BE test.

2.2 BIAS EXTENSION (BE) TEST

BE is one of the two de facto standard test methods used to measure the in-plane intraply shear behavior for the fabrics and preregs. The BE testing requires a rectangular specimen of the material to be clamped in the flat grips and the selection of suitable deformation rate and temperature conditions, especially in the case of prepreg testing. The length of the specimen is typically double or

more than its width. The orientation of the fibers is maintained at $\pm 45^\circ$ to the loading direction in the undeformed configuration. The overall size of the BE specimen in these particular tests is 250 mm in length and 74 mm in width (effective gauge dimensions of '220 mm \times 74 mm'). The shear angle γ (radians) measured theoretically in the pure shear zone of the BE specimen [10] is:

$$\gamma = 90^\circ - 2 \cdot \text{acos} \left(\frac{L+\delta}{\sqrt{2} \times L} \right) \quad (1)$$

Where δ is the change in length of the specimen and $L = H - W$; where H and W are the original height and width of the specimen, respectively.

2.3 PICTURE FRAME (PF) TEST

PF tests is equally popular in measuring the intraply shear behavior of thermoset and thermoplastic composites with continuous reinforced fibers including textile materials [10-12]. In the PF test, the fabric sample is initially square and held in the test-rig in such a way that the tows are oriented in the $\pm 45^\circ$ position to the loading direction. The tows of fibrous reinforcement are maintained parallel to the outer edges of the sample as well as clamping plates of the jig. PF is a pure shear test for the entire specimen under investigation. The effective specimen size used for the PF tests is 136 mm \times 136 mm. The shear angle, γ , can be calculated from the geometry of the picture frame [10] as:

$$\gamma = 90^\circ - 2 \cdot \text{acos} \left(\frac{\sqrt{2}L_{frame}+d}{2 \times L_{frame}} \right) \quad (2)$$

Where L_{frame} is the side length of the PF jig and δ is the extension applied on the specimen.

Both PF and BE tests were performed on Instron-5800R universal testing machine equipped with an environmental chamber using load-cells of 500N and 1kN capacity. The test conditions for both methods using different temperature and deformation rates are summarized in Table 1. All tests for temperature effects at performed at a single stretch rate (1mm/sec) and strain rate effects are studied at room temperature only. Each test was repeated for a minimum of five times and the graphs are plotted as average of the test data.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 BE TEST RESULTS

The BE test results are presented as overall applied force (N) versus shear angle ($^\circ$) computed in the pure shear zone of the specimen. This form of results largely fulfils the objectives of the study.

3.1.1 WOVEN PREPREG

The intraply shear results for the woven prepreg are presented along with that of the constituent dry fabric reinforcement. Figure 2a shows the comparison between the shear behaviour of the prepreg and its dry reinforcement. It can be observed from the force-shear curves that there is a continuous decrease in the magnitude of force with increasing temperature required to deform the material in shear. However, the most significant decrease occurs from RT (room temperature, 21 $^\circ$ C) to 40 $^\circ$ C. This is very clear when examining Figure 2b, which shows the applied force at 40 $^\circ$ shear angle from RT to 80 $^\circ$ C (including the constituent dry fabric data as a comparator). The applied force at 40 $^\circ$ shear drops by 60% of the RT value when heating up to 40 $^\circ$ C and subsequently only by approximately 10% of the original (RT) force value heating to 60 $^\circ$ C and then 80 $^\circ$ C successively. This behaviour can be anticipated due to the change of viscosity of the resin as shown in the temperature-dependent viscosity curves in Figure 1.

Figure 2. BE test results woven prepreg at different temperatures and its corresponding dry fabric at an axial stretch rate of 1 mm/sec

The woven prepreg intraply shear behaviour is found to converge towards that of the dry woven fabric at only moderately elevated temperatures (~80°C). At these moderate temperatures and at higher shear angles (~50°), the shear resistance of the woven prepreg can be observed lower than that of the dry fabric. This can be attributed to the state of resin at 80°C, which acts as a lubricant and assists the shear deformation of prepreg tows. It can also be speculated that the prepreg deformation at higher shear angles having low viscosity resin promotes inter-tow slippage that is usually observed in the case of dry fabrics.

3.1.1 NCF PREPREG

Figure 3a shows the effect of temperature on the intraply shear behaviour of pillar-stitched prepreg along ST (stitching tensile) direction for three different temperature states i.e. RT, 40 °C and 60 °C. It can be observed that there is a significant change in the magnitude of force between RT and 40 °C test results. However, the shear behaviour of pillar-stitched prepreg is only marginally affected from 40 °C up to 60 °C. This is in line with the temperature-dependent viscous behaviour of resin as shown in Figure 1 where the viscosity of Resin#2 also drops significantly from RT to 40°C but less so continuing up to 60 °C.

Figure 3. BE test results NCF prepreg along ST orientation at different temperatures and its corresponding dry fabric at an axial stretch rate of 1 mm/sec

Figure 3b shows the applied force at 40° shear angle, for NCF prepreg in ST orientation, from RT to 60 °C. A similar trend in the drop of applied force can be observed for the NCF prepreg as was observed for the woven prepreg. The applied force at 40° shear drops by 31% of the RT value when heating up to 40 °C and subsequently only by approximately 12% of the original (RT) force value heating to 60 °C. It can be observed in the curves presented in Figure 3 that the temperature-dependent behaviour at 40°C and 60°C corresponds to that of the dry fabric up to a shear angle of ~40°. It should be noted here that the intraply shear behaviour of NCF prepreg beyond ~40° of shear angle is inconsistent and unreliable due to continuous rupture of the fabric stitches.

The BE testing for the SC (stitching compression) orientation of the NCF prepreg and its dry reinforcement is shown in Figure 4a. It can be observed again that the resin significantly affects the force required to shear the prepreg whereas the shearing force is very low in the case of dry fabric only. It can also be observed that the shear response of the NCF material in SC orientation is analogous to that of the woven materials. Figure 4b shows the applied force at 40° shear angle, for the NCF prepreg in SC orientation, from RT to 60 °C. Again, the data describing the behaviour of the constituent dry fabric is included for comparison. The applied force at 40° shear drops by 85% of the RT value when heating up to 40 °C and subsequently only by approximately 8% of the original (RT) force value heating to 60 °C.

Figure 4. BE test results NCF prepreg along SC orientation at different temperatures and its corresponding dry fabric at an axial stretch rate of 1 mm/sec

BE tests for the NCF prepreg were also performed to observe the strain rate effect. Figure 5 shows the intraply shear behaviour of the prepreg using deformation rates of 0.5, 1 and 2 mm/sec determined at RT. The results clearly indicate the influence of strain rate on the force required to deform the material in shear. This difference in the shear force due to varying strain rates can only be attributed to the viscoelastic nature of the resin.

Figure 5. A comparison of BE test results for the pillar stitched prepreg along SC direction at deformation rates of 0.5mm/sec, 1mm/sec and 2mm/sec

3.2 PF TEST RESULTS

3.2.1 WOVEN PREPREG

The influence of temperature on woven prepreg, with PF testing, shown in Figure 6a has been presented for the different temperature conditions of RT, 40 °C, 60 °C and 80 °C. The results show a continuous drop in the applied force with the increase of prepreg temperature as witnessed in the BE testing. It can be observed here that the difference in maximum level of force observed at a shear angle 40° is quite insignificant. However, the difference in force to shear deform the woven prepreg from RT to 40°C test at a shear angle of 40° is quite considerable i.e. ~113N to ~27N respectively (for the deformation rate of 1mm/sec).

Figure 6b shows the test results for woven prepreg characterised at selected deformation rates of 0.5 mm/sec, 1 mm/sec and 2 mm/sec. The locking angle (a measure of the drapability of a fabric) estimated for the woven prepreg using PF testing shown in Figure 6b at the deformation rate of 2 mm/sec is ~46°. The locking angle determined from PF and BE testing for the woven prepreg are observed to be quite consistent indeed. It can also be noted in Figure 6b that the locking angle increases as the prepreg deformation rate decreases.

Figure 6. PF test results for the woven prepreg

3.2.2 NCF PREPREG

Figure 7a shows a comparison of the PF test results for NCF prepreg at RT and at 40 °C along ST direction at a single deformation rate of 1 mm/sec. In the case of stitched prepreg using PF test method, when increasing the material temperature from RT to 40 °C the force required in order to deform the material in shear drops significantly i.e. 245 N to 140 N at ~30° of shear angle. It can be observed from Figure 7a that the resistance to shear deformation is comparatively high in the region OA due to limited movement of the stitches impeded by the viscous resin state; this somewhat reduces in the region AB due to slackening of stitches. The region BC shows a proper (unimpeded) shear response of the material up to about 40° of shear angle. Beyond point C the shear behaviour data is erratic due to rupture of the fabric stitches. The prepreg material is fully restrained on the external edges in the case of PF testing that creates a difference as compared to BE test results shown in Figure 3a.

The intraply shear behaviour with varying temperature (RT and 40 °C) in the case of SC orientation of the NCF prepreg is shown in Figure 7b. It can be observed that the intraply shear behaviour of the prepreg along SC orientation evaluated by PF testing is equivalent in trend, of the applied force versus shear angle, to that of the woven materials. However, there is a significant difference in the trend and magnitude of the applied force at different shear angles of the material.

Figure 7. PF test results of NCF prepreg at two different temperatures using an axial stretch rate of 1 mm/sec

4 CONCLUSIONS

The current research work presents an experimental investigation to analyse the intraply shear behaviour of thermoset prepregs. Two types of prepregs were characterised using BE and PF tests. Varying temperatures and deformation rates were used to study the in-plane intraply shear deformation behaviour of the candidate materials. The results indicate that intraply shear behaviour of a prepreg material is strongly controlled by the resin and its viscosity state; the resin has a significant influence on the force applied and ultimately determines the locking angle of the material, again dependent upon the viscosity of resin. It has been determined with this study that the intraply shear behaviour of selected thermoset prepregs and that of the constituent dry fabric reinforcements converge at only moderately elevated temperatures, suggesting that optimal preforming (with the aims of increasing the locking angle of a prepreg fabric) can be carried out at temperatures well below that of the onset of cure.

The applied strain rate has been shown to have a significant effect on the intraply shear behaviour of a prepreg, suggesting that a careful selection of automatic preforming rate can lead to improved formability results. The in-plane shear characterisation tests of a pillar-stitched NCF prepreg for ST direction confirm that the shear data is useful to a shear angle of ~40°. Thereafter, the fabric stitches are broken and the obtained shear force data is inconsistent and irregular for both PF and BE testing.

The difference in trends of the curves obtained from PF and BE testing for the NCF prepreg also reveal the influence of boundary conditions on the specimen.

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